

Bayesian risk modelling of the Hyperloop system

Kumar. A

Karsten Moholt AS, Bergen, Norway

Hegde. J

Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway

Edwin. J. E

Safetec Nordic AS, Trondheim, Norway

ABSTRACT: This paper proposes a qualitative Bayesian risk model for the Hyperloop system. The paper identifies key technical risk factors, which may be involved in the future operations of Hyperloop systems. Thirty-four technical risk factors are identified and assessed for relationships with each other. A qualitative Bayesian Belief Network (BBN) is constructed to structure and map the relationships of identified risk factors. The results of the paper can help in identifying and structuring risk factors, which can be used as an input by the Hyperloop system designers. In addition, the proposed BBN model can also allow for easy interpretation of technical risk factors amongst personnel from different disciplines.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the year 2012, a conceptual passenger and freight transportation system known as the Hyperloop system was proposed by Musk (2013). The Hyperloop system is proposed to consist of pressurized capsules ridden on air bearings, which travel in low-pressure tubes by using linear induction motors and air compressors (Musk, 2013). Currently, different consortia are trying to popularize the Hyperloop concept by adapting and analysing its feasibility using the current available technology (Battenberg & Springer, 2017; Hyperloop Transportation Technologies, 2015; Macdonald, 2017; The University of Edinburgh, 2017; Zeleros, 2018).

Although Hyperloop system promises faster travel times to destinations, it may also be susceptible to technical and operational failures. Identifying possible failure scenarios and knowing the relationship between the risk factors is vital to ensure safety of the Hyperloop system, the critical infrastructure and the human passengers. Currently, the literature provides limited reliability, availability, maintainability and safety (RAMS) requirements for the Hyperloop system.

The University of Edinburgh (2017) has previously investigated the use of failure mode effect analysis (FMEA) to identify the local and global effects of component failures in a Hyperloop system. D. Zhou, Xin, Hessami, & Wang (2015) propose a model-based HAZOP method to identify hazards during the operation of the Hyperloop systems. However, as development of Hyperloop systems are still in a nascent stage, the

possible failure scenarios should be analysed using a flexible risk model, which is easy to interpret by all stakeholders. An FMEA analysis or model-based HAZOP are not suitable during the operational phase. The risk modelling approach should ideally allow for both qualitative and quantitative risk modelling.

According to Sigurdsson, Walls, & Quigley (2001) a Bayesian Belief Network (BBN) is a suitable tool to map dependencies between system variables. BBN's have been shown to aid in risk modelling within high risk industries such as the offshore / subsea oil and gas industry (Brito & Griffiths, 2016; Gran et al., 2012; Røed, Mosleh, Vinnem, & Aven, 2009; Vinnem et al., 2012).

This paper aims to provide an overview of the current state-of-the-art of the Hyperloop system. The main objective of this paper is to propose a qualitative Bayesian risk model based on the states of the various sub-systems of the Hyperloop system. Potential failure scenarios and their effects on the overall safety level of the Hyperloop system may be deduced from the proposed BBN. The results from this paper can be used by system developers to design safer Hyperloop system architectures.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the method used in this paper. Section 3 provides a generic description of the Hyperloop system. The proposed Bayesian Belief Network is presented in Section 4 followed by a brief discussion in Section 5. Section 6 presents the conclusions and identifies future work opportunities.

2 METHOD

Figure 1 illustrates the two parts of the method used in this paper. As numerous Hyperloop systems are either in their conceptual, design or testing phases, it is a challenge to comprehend the generic system architecture of the Hyperloop system. Part 1 addresses this challenge by reviewing existing Hyperloop systems and describing the key elements of an Hyperloop system. This overview is an important input to Part 2 of the method; the development of BBN.

Figure 1 Method used in this paper

Part 2 of the method consists of five steps. In Step 1, a target node is identified. A target node can signify either a failure event or a successful event. This steps aids in limiting the scope of the proposed BBN. In Step 2, all relevant nodes are identified, which can affect the state of the target node. In Step 3, the nodes are structured by connecting the nodes to each other and capture their interdependencies. Modes of operation of the system can

be used to identify the interdependencies among the components making the Hyperloop system.

Each node in the BBN can have several states, which can be identified through Step 4. States of the node signify the discrete number of changes possible for a given node. In Step 5, the assumed casual relationships in the BBN are scrutinized in an iterative manner. The causalities and the connecting arcs are changed as necessary.

3 SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Hyperloop is a means of transport of high speed and low energy consumption (Musk, 2013). However, the concept on which this means of transport is based was formulated at the beginning of the 20th century (Goddard, 1945). Two versions of the Hyperloop system have previously been proposed; a passenger version and a freight version (Musk, 2013). In this paper, the Hyperloop system description is based on the passenger only version of the system. The Hyperloop consists of several distinct components carrying out several functions.

Table 1 shows the primary required functions of Hyperloop system. The proposed seven modes of Hyperloop transit are stop, initial motion mode, critical speed mode, stable movement mode, initial acceleration mode, terminal deceleration mode and the stop mode. As observed in Table 1, the six key functions which are required in all modes of operations are on-board battery system, control system, partial vacuum tube, pylons, capsule and the communication system. Figure 2 illustrates only the primary sub-systems of the Hyperloop system, which is adapted from Musk (2013) and MIT Hyperloop Team, (2017).

3.1 Capsule

Capsule is a pressurized vessel, which houses all the physical systems for levitation, suspension, propulsion, on-board energy supply, control and communication. The pressure inside the capsule is maintained at atmospheric pressure as it is required for the human passengers

Table 1 Primary required functions during different modes of operations

	Stop	Initial motion	Critical speed	Stable movement	Initial deceleration	Terminal deceleration	Stop
Friction braking							
Eddy current braking							
Levitation							
Suspension							
Low speed propulsion							
Partial vacuum tube							
High speed propulsion							
On-board battery system							
Control system							
Communication							
Pylons							
Stations							
Capsule							

(Musk, 2013). The front of the capsule houses the axial compressor to reduce aerodynamic drag. Hyperloop One and Hyperloop Transportation Technologies (HTT) have unveiled the first version of their capsules and both use a form of carbon fibre for the outer shell of the capsule to reduce the weight, friction and to achieve maximum possible mechanical strength (HyperloopOne, 2017; Jaquith, 2016).

magnetic levitation is advantageous compared to other levitation approaches as it requires zero power input when the capsule is in motion.

The passive levitation mechanism results in high stiffness and low damping at cruising speeds, which would result in large, under-damped vibrations in the pod and skis (MIT Hyperloop Team, 2017; The University of Edinburgh, 2017). It could create discomfort for passengers on-board. To overcome this problem, each magnetic array is installed on a ski that has active

Figure 2 Illustration of a generic Hyperloop system adapted from Musk (2013) and MIT Hyperloop team (2017)

3.2 Levitation and suspension

Passive magnetic levitation is the technology used by multiple consortia (Battenberg & Springer, 2017; Geuss, 2016; Handmer, 2016; Janzen, 2017; MIT Hyperloop Team, 2017) and is based on electrodynamic suspension (EDS). The maglev system for *passive magnetic levitation* relies on magnets placed in an array on the underside of the capsule. The magnetic field hence created is called primary magnetic field. The primary magnetic field induces eddy currents in the conductive surfaces like aluminium or copper or over non-powered electromagnetic coils on the rail beneath the train, which creates a secondary magnetic field. The secondary magnetic field repels the primary magnetic field when the pod starts moving and generates enough repulsion force above the critical speed, thereby creating levitation.

The critical speed changes depending on the magnet array configuration. The system does not require external power and therefore is easily scalable because of the efficiency and safety at high speeds. One of the magnetic array configurations is Halbach array, which was used by Lawrence Livermore National Labs in California to develop Inductrack (Post, 2003). In this configuration, the array focuses the magnetic field of a set of magnets on one side of the array while cancelling out the field on the opposite side. The magnetic fields under the capsule result in levitation forces at even low speeds (Ross, 2016). Decker et al., (2017) also suggest that passive

mechanical dampers ensuring a smooth ride for passengers.

3.3 Propulsion

Linear Motor: The capsule is propelled using contactless linear electric motor, which is a straightened-out version of a conventional rotary motor and placed at intervals along the tube (Janzen, 2017; Musk, 2013). A conventional electric motor has two primary parts: a stator (the part that stays still) and a rotor (the part that moves or rotates). When the stator is powered up, it makes the rotor spin due to electromagnetic induction. A linear electric motor works on the same principle, however, the rotor does not rotate, instead moves in a straight line along the length of the stator. The stators are mounted along some sections of the tube, which generate alternating magnetic field to accelerate the pod (Jetti et al., 2017). The rotor is mounted to the pod, and the pod straddles the stators as it accelerates down the tube. In the system described in this paper, a permanent magnet linear synchronous motor is assumed in which the rotor is a permanent magnet array (Abdelrahman, Sayeed, & Youssef, 2018) and the stator is made of electromagnets being activated using frequency converters powered by alternating current (Jetti et al., 2017).

Compressor: In order to maintain partial vacuum, Musk (2013) proposes that a residual air pressure of 100 Pa (0.001 bar) is economically viable as it can be achieved using standard pumps and with an acceptable level of

energy consumption. However, at transonic speeds, the flow around the pod will start to choke and the mass around the flow would be maximum – the Kantrowitz limit (Kantrowitz & Donaldson, 1945). Therefore, a compressor is needed with the following main purposes:

a) Reduce the drag created during the movement of the capsule in partial vacuum.

b) Create thrust by releasing the compressed air through the nozzle located at the end of the capsule (Musk, 2013).

Many consortia namely, WARR Hyperloop (Battenberg & Springer, 2017), HTT (Hyperloop Transportation Technologies, 2015) and Transpod (Janzen, 2017) are using axial compressor at the front of the capsule. The system described in this paper uses an axial compressor as it has been practically demonstrated by WARR Hyperloop at SpaceX Hyperloop pod competition (Battenberg & Springer, 2017). The pod won the Hyperloop pod design competition because of the compressor on board and scored highly in the scalability criteria as well (Technical University of Munich Campus news, 2017).

Low speed and Emergency Propulsion: The capsule uses propulsion motor driven wheels for low speed and emergency propulsion (Battenberg & Springer, 2017; MIT Hyperloop Team, 2017; Delft Hyperloop, 2018). A minimum critical speed needs to be attained before passive magnetic levitation can levitate the capsule. While braking, the capsule makes contact with the rails and the wheels are engaged to drive the capsule to a stop position.

3.4 *Braking and deceleration:*

Linear motor: The polarity of the electromagnets in the stator is reversed to produce deceleration (Abdelrahman et al., 2018). This can be performed during transition from high speed to lower speed.

Eddy current and Friction braking: After the capsule starts decelerating, permanent magnets arranged in Halbach array are moved closer to the I-beam the using pneumatic/hydraulic actuators. The magnetic array induces eddy currents in the I-beam and hence produces a repulsive magnetic field (drag) (Bambrogan & Giegel, 2016; MIT Hyperloop Team, 2017; Battenberg & Springer, 2017). This way, the fail-safe brakes avoid contact with the rail and avoid any form of wear. The main difficulty arises from accurate actuation to get a small air gap and maximise drag. To stop the array from contacting the rail there are mechanical stoppers on the brackets. Brakes can be extended partially to compensate for lateral displacement and oscillations as well. A fail-safe actuator system is used for the friction braking as well (MIT Hyperloop Team, 2017; The University of Edinburgh, 2017). The friction brakes are retracted using hydraulics and engaged during low-speed using a gas

cylinder in hydraulic system meaning that the system will be automatically activated in the event of power failure (The University of Edinburgh, 2017).

3.5 *Energy Supply*

Energy to power the capsule is stored in batteries for supplying power to the propulsion system, the control system and the braking system (Musk, 2013). The batteries are enclosed in a housing, which maintains atmospheric pressure and protects the batteries from vacuum (Battenberg & Springer, 2017; European Space Agency, 2018). The energy supply for the tube comes from renewable sources like solar panels mounted on top of the tube (Johnston, 2018; Musk, 2013)

3.6 *Partially evacuated tube*

Two partially evacuated steel cylindrical tubes are welded together in a side by side configuration to allow the capsules to travel in both directions (Musk, 2013). Vacuum pumps are installed along the tube to maintain the partial vacuum environment inside the tube. To avoid shock wave formation around the capsule, the capsule size and tube size must suitable. Hyperloop Transportation Technologies, (2015) proposes other kind of materials namely corrugated steel and fiberglass which can be used for construction of tube.

3.7 *Pylons*

Pylons of the Hyperloop system are designed to allow longitudinal slip for thermal expansion but must constrain the tube in the vertical direction. The minimally constrained pillars to tube joints ensure a smoother ride. Structural simulations have shown that the structural integrity of the Hyperloop is not compromised in presence of atmospheric pressure, tube weight, earthquakes, winds, etc. (Musk, 2013). Dampers will be required to absorb the vibrations at points where the pylons and tubes meet. The dampers need to also isolate movements in the ground from the tube (Musk, 2013). Gate valves and vacuum pumps are installed at every pylon. Emergency exits are also needed at every pylon (Gresta, 2017).

3.8 *Station*

The system described in this paper discusses the station as designed in Zhou (2017) by HTT. The station comprises of platforms, tube and gates at the platform.

Platform: Platforms are needed to hold people waiting to enter and exit the Hyperloop capsule(s).

Tube: The partially evacuated tube described in Section 3.5 continues in the station and the incoming tube diverges into a plurality of tracks within the tube at the station. Each track is adapted to carry a capsule. The

capsule enters the station and exits the station from the same side of the station on which the tube enters.

Gates at the platform: The incoming capsule is docked at the platform with gates which are located on one side of the tube. Each gate comprises of a door which forms a barrier between the low-pressure environment of the tube and an exterior of the tube. A component of the gate forms a seal with the exterior of capsule allowing the door of the capsule to open and for people to enter and exit the capsule.

3.9 Communication and Centralized traffic control system

Accelerators and tracking sensors are used to track the pod's location in the tube. The sensor system measures the distance to the end of the tube and communicates other operating parameters to the centralized traffic control system. These systems are crucial in controlling pod speeds throughout the tube and in tracking down pods in the event of a system failure.

4 BAYESIAN BELIEF NETWORK

This section describes the Part 2 of the method as illustrated in Figure 1. The scope of this section is to describe the rationale used to construct the proposed BBN as shown in Figure 3.

The first step in developing the BBN is to describe the top node or the node which is affected by all other nodes. In a BBN, such a node is called a target node. It is to be noted that a different target node would result in a change in the scope of the BBN. In case of an Hyperloop system, the safe operation of Hyperloop system is paramount

given the different technical systems which can fail. For this reason, the target node, in the proposed BBN is chosen to be the “Safe Hyperloop operation” illustrated in dark green shading in Figure 3.

Step 2 of the BBN process is to identify the relevant nodes affecting the target node. Nodes can be identified by studying the system and mapping the interdependencies between the target node. The system description in Section 3 provided an input to this step. To keep the scope limited, only technical factors affecting the safe operation of the Hyperloop system are considered in this paper. In addition, the functional requirements shown in Table 1 also provide information on different sub-systems of the Hyperloop system and their sequence of activation. In total, this step resulted in thirty-four different nodes as shown in Figure 3. The components providing primary functions are shown with bright green shading Figure 3.

The on-board battery, tube pumps, gate valves, and station pumps are dependent on external electric supply. The on-board battery system powers the control system, the communication system, low speed propulsion and the high-speed propulsion system. The suspension system is dependent on the control system to provide updated values of required damping for the capsule. Similarly, the control system also needs to provide input to the eddy current braking system. Without the eddy current braking system, the capsule will not be able to brake from a high-speed propulsion mode to low speed mode. Suspension system also ensures that the effect of levitation is constant along the path.

Motor driven wheels are necessary to achieve low speed propulsion. In low speed mode, the friction braking system is activated, typically during approach to stations

Figure 3 Proposed Bayesian Belief Network of an Hyperloop system

or during emergencies. To achieve the safe high-speed propulsion, the linear motor, the eddy current braking system and the compressor on the front of the capsule are required. The control system regulates the operation of motor driven wheels, the compressor, pneumatic or hydraulic supply and friction braking system depending on the modes of operation listed in Table 1.

In relation to the infrastructure, the pylons are dependent on availability of vibration sensors readings and the dampers, which isolate the environment inside the tube from external factors affecting the tube. The vacuum required for the partially evacuated tubes are achieved by the pumps at different locations and gate valves can be used to form air locks along the tube and at the stations. Safe working of stations is dependent on functioning gates at the platforms used for entry and exit of passengers and station pumps keeping the partial vacuum environment in the tubes at the station.

Table 2 Possible states of nodes in the proposed BBN

Node	States
External electric supply (solar, wind)	Available, unavailable
On-board battery system	Fully charged, partially charged, fully discharged
Rail array	Structurally intact, cracked, broken
Capsule – magnetic array	Functioning, degraded, failed
Levitation system	Functioning, degraded, failed
Dampers	Functioning, degraded, failed
Vibration sensors	Functioning, degraded, failed
Suspension system	Functioning, degraded, failed
Control system	Functioning, degraded, failed
Pneumatic or hydraulic supply	Available, degraded, unavailable
Magnetic array for braking	Functioning, degraded, failed
Rail – I beam	Structurally intact, cracked, broken
Eddy current braking system	Functioning, degraded, failed
Capsule communication system	Functioning, degraded, failed
Capsule	Structurally intact, degraded structurally compromised
Friction braking	Functioning, degraded, failed
Motor driven wheels	No wear, mild wear, worn out
Linear motor	Functioning, degraded, failed
Low speed propulsion system	Functioning, degraded, failed
High speed propulsion system	Functioning, degraded, failed
Compressor	Functioning, degraded, failed
Pylons	Structurally intact, cracked, broken
Vibration sensors	Functioning, degraded, failed
Dampers	Functioning, degraded, failed
Tube pumps	Functioning, degraded, failed
Gate valves	Functioning, degraded, failed
Partially evacuated tube	Functioning, degraded, failed
Station pumps	Functioning, degraded, failed
Gates at platform	Functioning, degraded, failed
Stations	Available, unavailable

Finally, the states of the communication and centralized traffic control system, the low speed propulsion system, high speed propulsion system, the eddy current braking system, pylons, stations, capsule and partially evacuated

tubes influence the identified target node; safe Hyperloop operation.

If any of the nodes representing primary functions (bright green nodes in Figure 3) change to a degraded state, the state of Hyperloop operation will no longer be safe and hence emergency mode will have to be activated. The risk introduced due to the degraded state is high because of three reasons; a) it endangers the life of the passengers travelling in the capsule; b) it might affect the functioning of other primary functions leading to more extreme consequences and c) it negatively impacts the reputation of a new and emerging mode of transport.

In case of emergency mode, depending on the type of the root cause, the capsule is brought to either stand-still using the eddy-braking system and friction braking or is propelled to the next station (Gresta, 2017; HyperloopOne, 2018). In case of emergency stop, it is vital that the pod stops between two pylons. The centralized traffic control system coordinates the emergency stop. The gate valves on the pylons are activated and form the airlock and re-pressurize that section. Each capsule and pylons can have built-in emergency exits.

Step 4 of the process ensures that the identified nodes are allocated discrete possible states. For example, the on-board battery system is allocated three states i.e., fully charged, partially charged, and fully discharged. The possible states of the nodes in Figure 3 are listed in Table 2. The proposed BBN as shown in Figure 3 has undergone numerous iterations during the development of the BBN. The proposed BBN is ensured to map the real-life dependencies of the identified nodes on the target node.

5 DISCUSSION

This section presents the observations made during the development of the proposed BBN. The following observations are discussed in brief

- Key findings from the proposed BBN.
- Standardization of system architecture.
- Challenges of using BBN for risk modelling.
- Influence of external risk factors.
- Dependency on critical infrastructure.

Key findings from the proposed BBN

The proposed BBN as illustrated in Figure 3, shows that the Hyperloop is a complex system with many different independent technical sub-systems, which can influence the safe operation. The battery system and the control system can be observed to influence the state of many other sub-systems.

From the proposed BBN it can also be deduced that the Hyperloop system will require numerous sub-systems to be available simultaneously. Some of these sub-systems

may need to be redundant. The system architects will therefore need to consider the strategy for redundant components in the sub-system to ensure high system availability. The designed component / sub-system redundancy will also affect the maintenance strategy and can influence the overall design / operating cost.

The proposed BBN has limited the scope to a sub-system level. A deeper component level BBN may also be required in the future where each component state can be classified during real-time operation. The state of component can further be used to update the component level BBN.

Standardization of system architecture

As mentioned in Section 1, there are numerous Hyperloop systems under development each with its unique system architecture. Although variety in system design during initial development stages can be expected, it cannot be sustainable in the long-run. Stakeholders of the Hyperloop system will need to standardize some aspects of the system.

Currently, industry partners from Europe and Canada are collaborating to establish an international framework for developing standards for Hyperloop to ensure that the upcoming solutions meet the safety and regulatory requirements (Zeleros, 2018). This step will eventually lead to a standardized Hyperloop system with reduced variation and complexity with respect to the system architecture. The system description provided in Section 3 may therefore differ from future Hyperloop designs. However, the proposed BBN can be easily adapted according to the chosen system architecture. This is also one of the advantages of using BBNs for risk modelling.

Challenges of using BBN for risk modelling

Although, BBNs are suitable for risk modelling of complex systems, they can also be susceptible to modelling errors and / or misinterpretations. The number of nodes in a BBN can influence the ease of interpreting the network i.e., as the number of nodes increase, the structure of the BBN may be difficult to validate. Also, the number of nodes and their states can influence the ability to quantify the BBN as they result in an increase in conditional probability tables (CPTs).

Information basis for generating CPTs is not available yet due to lack of test and failure data of the Hyperloop system. The design standards for a functional Hyperloop at an industrial scale is not materialized yet; hence this poses challenges in finding the right quality of data, collected for desired configuration of the Hyperloop system or sub-systems. Therefore, this paper has not considered the quantification of the proposed BBN. Currently, the literature provides numerous methods to quantify BBNs both with and without involvement of

experts in the elicitation process (Mkrtychyan, Podofillini, & Dang, 2015, 2016).

Influence of external risk factors

To limit the scope of this paper, external risk influencing factors, such as environmental conditions, human and organizational factors are not considered in the proposed BBN. This may however also be vital when analysing the overall availability of the Hyperloop system. External factors may also influence the availability of the technical systems, for example, natural disasters can result in an unavailable Hyperloop system. In addition, human and organization factors, such as fatigue, organizational safety culture and regulatory pressures may also influence the safe operation of the Hyperloop system.

Dependency on critical infrastructure

Hyperloop technology has still not reached the technology readiness levels where it can be scaled easily. The systems need testing at an industrial scale contrary to small-scale testing. This is true in case of Hyperloop One, who currently have access to only small-scale testing facility (HyperloopOne, 2018b). The critical infrastructure like the long partially evacuated tubes, pylons and passive magnetic levitation among others need to be tested at industrial scale for establishing high reliability.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Since the year 2013, numerous private and public stakeholders have been working to realize and test the Hyperloop system. This includes multimillion dollar companies and research institutes. To increase the technology readiness level of the Hyperloop system, reliability and safety requirements are also needed to be developed.

This paper provides the state-of-the-art on the topic of Hyperloop system development. A generic system description is provided by reviewing relevant publicly available literature of the Hyperloop system, which are under development. The paper contributes to the body of knowledge by proposing a qualitative and visual risk model based on Bayesian Belief Network (BBN). The proposed BBN consists of thirty-four unique technical risk factors (nodes), which can influence the safe operation of the Hyperloop system. Such a risk model can aid in the system development phase by communicating the various technical risk factors to personnel working on a wide variety of engineering disciplines. This information can further be used by system developers to ensure sufficient safety margins / redundancies are in place to avoid a single point failure in the Hyperloop system.

Future research scope is to convert the proposed qualitative BBN risk model to a quantitative model. The model may then be used to predict the failure / success of operations given relevant information on the state of the identified nodes. The proposed BBN may also be extended to incorporate external risk influencing factors, such as human, natural and organizational factors.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge the support from their respective employers. The authors would also like to thank the anonymous reviewers for their inputs to this paper.

REFERENCES

- Abdelrahman, A. S., Sayeed, J., & Youssef, M. Z. (2018). Hyperloop Transportation System: Analysis, Design, Control, and Implementation. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 65(9), 7427–7436. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2017.2777412>
- Bambrogan, B., & Giegel, J. (2016, August 11). Transportation system. Google Patents.
- Battenberg, A., & Springer, M. (2017). Lightweight Design Concept for a Vacuum-tube Jet. *Lightweight Design Worldwide*, 10(2), 24–29.
- Brito, M., & Griffiths, G. (2016). A Bayesian approach for predicting risk of autonomous underwater vehicle loss during their missions. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 146, 55–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2015.10.004>
- Delft Hyperloop. (2018). *Delft Hyperloop II - Design Presentation ATLAS 01*. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y0SNIFILeb4>
- European Space Agency. (2018). STUDENT HYPERLOOP MOTOR TESTED AT ESA. Retrieved June 27, 2018, from [https://www.esa.int/Our_Activities/Space_Engineering_Technology/Student_Hyperloop_motor_tested_at_ESA/\(print\)](https://www.esa.int/Our_Activities/Space_Engineering_Technology/Student_Hyperloop_motor_tested_at_ESA/(print))
- Geuss, M. (2016). Hyperloop company “exclusively licensed” passive magnetic levitation system. Retrieved June 11, 2018, from <https://arstechnica.com/information-technology/2016/05/hyperloop-company-exclusively-licensed-passive-magnetic-levitation-system/>
- Goddard, E. C. (1945). Vacuum tube transportation system.
- Gran, B. A., Bye, R., Nyheim, O. M., Okstad, E. H., Seljelid, J., Sklet, S., ... Vinnem, J. E. (2012). Evaluation of the Risk OMT model for maintenance work on major offshore process equipment. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 25(3), 582–593. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlp.2012.01.001>
- Gresta, B. (2017). *Hyperloop Transportation Technologies Creates the Future of Human Mobility*. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jECnDwRwfiA>
- Handmer, C. (2016). How and Why We’re Levitating the Hyperloop. Retrieved June 11, 2018, from <https://hyperloop-one.com/blog/how-and-why-were-levitating>
- Hyperloop Transportation Technologies. (2015). *Official Crowd Storm Document*. Retrieved from <https://lintvkrqe.files.wordpress.com/2014/12/crowdstor>
- m.pdf
- HyperloopOne. (2017). Hyperloop One Makes History with World’s First Successful Hyperloop Full Systems Test.
- HyperloopOne. (2018a). Facts and frequently asked questions. Retrieved June 30, 2018, from <https://hyperloop-one.com/facts-frequently-asked-questions>
- HyperloopOne. (2018b). First Look at DevLoop, World’s Only Full-Scale Hyperloop Test Track. Retrieved July 1, 2018, from <https://hyperloop-one.com/blog/first-look-devloop-worlds-only-full-scale-hyperloop-test-track>
- Janzen, R. (2017). TransPod Ultra-High-Speed Tube Transportation: Dynamics of Vehicles and Infrastructure. *Procedia Engineering*, 199, 8–17. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2017.09.142>
- Jaquith, T. (2016). Vibranium: Hyperloop Pods Will be Made From Super-Light “Smart Skin” That’s 10X Stronger Than Steel. Retrieved July 13, 2018, from <https://futurism.com/vibranium-hyperloop-pods-will-be-made-from-super-light-smart-skin-thats-10x-stronger-than-steel/>
- Jetti, S. R., Bambrogan, B., Giegel, J., O’neal, G., Bahrami, N., Dorris, J., & Liang, J. (2017, July 20). Dynamic linear stator segment control. Google Patents.
- Johnston, C. (2018). Q&A: Hyperloop CEO talks technology, vibranium and Black Panther. Retrieved June 27, 2018, from <http://www.tampabay.com/news/transportation/Q-A-Hyperloop-CEO-talks-technology-vibranium-and-Black-Panther-166959050>
- Kantrowitz, A., & Donaldson, C. (1945). *Preliminary Investigation of Supersonic Diffusers*. Retrieved from <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/archive/nasa/casi.ntrs.nasa.gov/19930093667.pdf>
- Macdonald, C. (2017). The Hyperloop is ready to go! First test track is complete as firm reveals 11 routes in the US that could use Elon Musk’s futuristic transport. Retrieved June 11, 2018, from <http://www.dailymail.co.uk/sciencetech/article-4387800/The-Hyperloop-ready-test-track-complete.html>
- MIT Hyperloop Team. (2017). *MIT Hyperloop Final Report*. Retrieved from http://hyperloop.mit.edu/uploads/7/6/1/8/76180385/mithyperloop_finalreport_2017_public.pdf
- Mkrtchyan, L., Podofilini, L., & Dang, V. N. (2015). Overview of methods to build Conditional Probability Tables with partial expert information for Bayesian Belief Networks. In *Safety and Reliability of Complex Engineered Systems* (pp. 1973–1981). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1201/b19094-257>
- Mkrtchyan, L., Podofilini, L., & Dang, V. N. (2016). Methods for building Conditional Probability Tables of Bayesian Belief Networks from limited judgment: An evaluation for Human Reliability Application. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 151, 93–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2016.01.004>
- Musk, E. (2013). *Hyperloop Alpha. SpaceX/Tesla Motors*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119171386>
- Post, R. F. (2003, October 7). Inductrack configuration. Google Patents.
- Røed, W., Mosleh, A., Vinnem, J. E., & Aven, T. (2009). On the use of the hybrid causal logic method in offshore risk analysis. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 94(2), 445–455. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2008.04.003>
- Sigurdsson, J. H., Walls, L. A., & Quigley, J. L. (2001). Bayesian belief nets for managing expert judgement and

- modelling reliability. *Quality and Reliability Engineering International*, 17(3), 181–190.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/qre.410>
- Technical University of Munich Campus news. (2017). SpaceX Hyperloop Competition: Showdown in Los Angeles. Retrieved June 28, 2018, from <https://www.tum.de/en/about-tum/news/press-releases/detail/article/33657/>
- The University of Edinburgh. (2017). *HypED Final Design Briefing*. Retrieved from https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5a0b00baace864b50ecccd8e/t/5a4502b5419202c4d35e0f2e/1514472183104/16%252F17+HypED_FDB_final.pdf
- Vinnem, J. E., Bye, R., Gran, B. A., Kongsvik, T., Nyheim, O. M., Okstad, E. H., ... Vatn, J. (2012). Risk modelling of maintenance work on major process equipment on offshore petroleum installations. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 25(2), 274–292.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlp.2011.11.001>
- Zeleros. (2018). Canadian and European Hyperloop Leaders Launch Industry-first Partnership to Establish International Standards and Regulatory Framework. Retrieved June 28, 2018, from <http://zeleros.com/hyperloop/>
- Zhou, D., Xin, W., Hessami, A., & Wang, H. (2015). Study on Model based Hazard Identification for the Hyperloop System. In *International Seminar on Computation, Communication and Control*.
- Zhou, Y. (2017, November 23). Station with loop configuration for hyperloop transportation system. Google Patents.